

RMID016

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.850$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.026$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.038$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.562$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID017

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.457$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.012$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.667$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.875$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.032c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID028

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.392$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.199$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.938$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.351$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$V_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID033

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.715$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.312$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.503$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.112$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID037

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.181$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.028$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.073$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.630$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID038

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.383$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.199$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.969$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.382$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID061

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.984$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.076$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.154$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.147$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID078

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.582$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.024$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.791$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.286$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID085

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.238$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.002$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.095$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.474$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.190c$$

$$P_y = 0.49$$

RMID088

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.517$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.021$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.529$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.963$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID101

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.458$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.190$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.957$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.351$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID102

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.861$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.329$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.086$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.718$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID114

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.226$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.236$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.293$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.780$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$V_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID118

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.715$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.252$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.319$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.833$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID134

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.964$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.221$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.243$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.702$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID160

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.360$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.015$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.206$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.508$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID177

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.482$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.026$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.446$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.983$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.034c$$

$$P_y = 0.54$$

RMID178

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.947$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.063$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.656$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.568$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID185

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.987$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.024$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.073$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.564$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.080c$$

$$P_y = 0.25$$

RMID191

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.442$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.068$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.553$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.499$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID193

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.003$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.437$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.799$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.554$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID202

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.635$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.604$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.613$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.508$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID204

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.923$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.115$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.863$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.038$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID243

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.659$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.027$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.587$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.129$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.029c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID250

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.285$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.106$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.706$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.846$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID260

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.995$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.562$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.111$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.975$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID265

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.736$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.046$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.408$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.187$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.035c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID267

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.588$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.114$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.956$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.127$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.011c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID268

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.651$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.009$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.676$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.725$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID272

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.263$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.058$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.970$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.850$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID275

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.577$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.038$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.491$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.181$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID296

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.120$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.187$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.856$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.243$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID300

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.646$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.219$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.128$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.583$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID301

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.548$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.018$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.573$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.947$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.025c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID304

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.492$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.116$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.926$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.104$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.057c$$

$$P_y = 0.30$$

RMID305

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.527$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.098$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.002$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.106$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID316

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.678$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.273$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.544$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.093$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID320

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.265$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.023$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.110$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.584$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID321

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.720$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.387$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.671$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.373$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID324

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.602$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.023$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.870$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.354$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID329

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.721$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.549$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.258$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.111$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID330

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.156$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.357$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.312$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.979$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID336

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.849$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.037$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.384$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.065$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID338

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.418$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.007$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.507$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.472$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.033c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID341

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.426$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.129$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.197$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.423$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID356

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.986$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.606$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.464$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.361$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID363

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.635$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.193$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.678$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 47.077$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID371

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.473$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.041$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.181$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.909$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID375

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.647$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.037$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.720$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.404$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID381

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.538$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.705$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.770$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.733$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID399

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.608$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.044$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.172$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.928$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID409

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.110$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.235$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.217$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.703$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID428

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.980$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.421$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.611$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.349$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID437

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.857$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.185$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.290$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.670$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID440

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.754$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.024$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.160$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.646$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID465

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.059$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.102$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.332$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.453$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.161c$$

$$P_y = 0.30$$

RMID478

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.956$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.035$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.830$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.484$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID492

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.964$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.142$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.728$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.995$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID493

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.592$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.079$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.655$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.668$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID510

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.710$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.025$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.417$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.921$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.018c$$

$$P_y = 0.30$$

RMID515

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.806$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.012$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.014$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.217$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID564

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.472$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.250$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.613$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 47.125$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID588

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.998$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.462$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.514$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.293$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID589

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.751$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.061$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.503$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.403$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID591

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.100$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.053$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.911$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.747$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID596

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.364$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.358$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.695$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.363$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID611

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.886$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.437$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.237$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.992$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$V_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID613

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.336$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.549$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.334$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 47.188$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID622

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.572$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.082$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.182$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.208$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID645

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.474$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.032$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.248$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.870$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.013c$$

$$P_y = 0.50$$

RMID656

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.801$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.220$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.001$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.457$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID664

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.840$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.109$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.334$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.487$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID676

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.515$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.149$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.821$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 47.108$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID692

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.642$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.116$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.192$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.370$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID694

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.532$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.343$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.498$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.147$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID701

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.683$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.042$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.470$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.212$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID714

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.921$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.029$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.919$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.500$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID720

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.467$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.079$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.145$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.156$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID733

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.455$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.024$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.254$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.752$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID736

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.583$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.100$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.565$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.679$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID746

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.683$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.187$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.107$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.494$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID753

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.562$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.372$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.496$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.180$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID761

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.771$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.074$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.512$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.495$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID762

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.783$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.029$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.859$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.442$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID768

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.259$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.005$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.783$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.569$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.025c$$

$$P_y = 0.40$$

RMID770

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.862$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.200$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 10.085$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 47.500$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID773

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.106$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.076$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.926$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.921$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID777

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 1.402$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.215$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.233$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.680$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$V_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID778

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.785$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.097$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.635$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.737$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID782

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.363$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.058$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.039$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.920$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID786

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 2.042$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.202$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 9.491$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 46.911$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID789

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.425$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.030$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.062$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.660$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID790

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.238$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.004$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.761$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.465$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID798

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.423$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.166$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.755$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 45.088$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID822

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.289$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.106$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 7.370$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.511$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = \text{N/A}$$

$$P_y = \text{N/A}$$

RMID840

AGN Parameters:

$$z = 0.244$$

$$\lambda_{Edd} = 0.004$$

$$\log_{10}(M_{BH}/M_{\odot}) = 8.511$$

$$\log_{10}(L_{bol}/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.206$$

Perturbation Parameters:

$$v_{10} = 0.020c$$

$$P_y = 0.40$$

